

Development and validation of mental health preparedness tool for incoming nursing students

Santanina D. Regueta, Sophia Isabel H. Dimayuga, Anna Minette T. Ortega, Jennifer Pineo,
 Keithra Erica C. Quitariano

Abstract

Mental health issues have contributed to the rising number of cases and among them are college students. Nursing students are exposed to stressors in their learning environment and are at risk of developing symptoms of mental health illnesses. The dominant explanation for this problem is inability to adapt to their educational environment as well as failure to strategize effective coping mechanisms. Despite acquiring studies related to the stress and mental illnesses of nursing students, the researchers faced difficulties in conducting research on exploring the mental health preparedness among incoming nursing students. The overall goal is to develop a mental health preparedness tool based on these factors to determine when an incoming nursing student is mentally prepared to be exposed to possible stressors in their learning environment. Researchers identified the experiences of nursing students and determined their adaptability process in the college program through the questionnaire data from Google Forms. Moreover, the researchers used thematic analysis to categorize the data into themes. The results showed the exposure of nursing students to stressors and symptoms of mental health problems. However, these students found ways to adapt to their environment and cope with the stressors.

Keywords: Development; Validation; Mental health preparedness tool; Nursing students.

Santanina D. Regueta*

Sophia Isabel H. Dimayuga

Anna Minette T. Ortega

Jennifer Pineo

Keithra Erica C. Quitariano

Nursing Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author

To cite this article:

Regueta, S. D., Dimayuga, S. I. H., Ortega, A. M. T., Pineo, J., & Quitariano, K. E. C. (2022). Development and validation of mental health preparedness tool for incoming nursing students. *SDCA Student Research Journal*, 10(1), 37-48.

Introduction

Mental readiness or mental preparedness is concurrence with an individual's thoughts and actions with their behavior (Damiano et al., 2017). Upon entering college, it is important for students to be prepared mentally. Conley (2007) mentioned that college instructors expect students to develop skills that do not develop extensively in high school. Most students assume that college courses would be similar to a high school class, leading to unpreparedness which can cause stress and failure to cope. To enhance one's performance, one must have self-confidence, concentration, and focus. Optimizing function is based on how mentally prepared an individual is. As a matter of fact, mental preparedness can help deal with challenging situations (Damiano, 2017).

However, many college students have reported dealing with stress throughout their time in school. Foreseeing potential hardships, students become pressured to pursue a college degree. Beauvais (2018) mentioned that students who are struggling to attain a college education stem from a lack of mental preparedness. Factors that bear a student's decision in going to college are: (1) Parents—they compare their children to their successful peers, in turn, placing more pressure on their children to do the same. A fresh, young high school graduate's choice can be altered through their parents' influence; (2) Peers—schoolmates, classmates, or those in the same age bracket may pass judgment on those who do not enter college. Most people believe that not getting an education will hinder their success.

Similarly, Conley (2007) expressed that to be successful in college is to learn unique ways of studying and coping skills. Students need to prepare mentally for a productive college life, away from much distress. Mental readiness is not only helpful in college, but also in their future careers. DeAngelis (2015) mentioned that students need to have an orientation about readiness because it pushes students to develop the skills they need to succeed. It is also essential to develop a student's mental readiness, to increase the chances of them thriving.

Mental preparedness is equally significant as mental health as it requires assessment in pretty much the same way. Students need to be well-equipped academically and emotionally. Understanding the concept of failure, knowing one's strengths and weaknesses, and self-care are all part of being mentally equipped. There is a certain level of maturity and determination needed in college (Reality Changers, 2017). In addition, Marinchak (2016), a licensed clinical psychologist, encountered many mentally unprepared students experiencing numerous challenges in college, such students coincidentally have mental health problems; to the extent of some students dropping out due to difficulty of balancing academics and mental well-being. Because of academic and social demands for training, freshmen exhibit varying learning strategies and coping mechanisms. For example, Shamsuddin et al. (2013) stated that a student's physical and mental health may be damaged by high academic expectations.

According to Rezayat and Nayeri (2014), stress, lack of assertiveness, and initiative among nursing students, make them more vulnerable to mental illness. Those students tend to perform poorly because of the clinical manifestations. Wynaden (2010) concluded that the lack of mental preparedness together with stressful events may lead to the lack of memory retention of students. Their capability in their future profession may be compromised as a result. To further support this claim, Barrett and Jackson (2013) reported that a nurse's lack of knowledge, confidence, competence and mental preparedness all led to insufficient quality of care to clients.

Therefore, institutions need to develop mental health policies and improve campus mental health services for students, especially for medical programs such as nursing as it is a 'managing people's health' type of profession. Barry and Ward (2016) also reported that incompetency by nurses today shows the need to review the mental preparedness and well-being of current nursing students to supplement them with the required skills for quality healthcare. It is important for students to master the art of caring upon graduation (Cheung et al., 2016).

In June 21, 2018, the Philippines established the first mental health act legislation in the country—R.A. 11036, also known as the Philippine Mental Health Act. It is a comprehensive structure for implementing excellent mental healthcare in the country. This act serves as a solution to the increasing number of mental illness cases through offering mental health services and programs across the nation. Senator Risa Hontiveros proposed this law over three years ago because the Philippines is among the countries with no mental health legislation at all (Lally et al., 2019).

Despite the efforts, the country remains unable to address the mental needs of Filipinos. According to Gonzales (2017), the Philippines still lack the facilities and mental health professionals to accommodate Filipinos with mental health disorders. In fact, most of the mental health professionals are living in the National Capital Region and cannot aide the 19 million Filipinos suffering from some kind of mental illness scattered across the country. The Philippines has approximately one (1) psychiatrist for every 250,000 Filipinos with psychiatric problems; unfortunately, this is far from the ideal ratio of 1 to 50,000 mentally ill patients.

Nurses play an important role in delivering the best quality of care. They are responsible for improving the quality of life that many patients. It is indeed important for college institutions to improve their mental health services for such vulnerable group because nursing students will be bare to obstacles in college before their start as registered nurses. The researchers are interested in the mental preparedness with particular emphasis on a student's mental well-being in pursuing a nursing career; they also conduct this research to determine which experiences of nursing students, from St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA), affect their mental health in order to develop and validate a mental health preparedness tool.

Moreover, the Mental Health Preparedness (MHP) tool accommodates nursing students by highlighting the importance of being prepared, both physically and mentally, in college. This will benefit the students as they prepare themselves by developing learning strategies and coping mechanisms needed in the tertiary level.

In addition, people in the institution will have increased awareness of mental wellness, which may improve the services and guidance provided to nursing students. This may decrease the stigma of mental health in the community. Nursing students having difficulties may also use the services available in the institution to determine early psychiatric symptoms and should have referral for adequate treatment by a professional. This will also help SDCA monitor the nursing students' mental well-being throughout their stay.

Research Questions

Kessler et al. (2007) estimated that 75% percent of onset mental disorders occur during college years. The students' experiences during their schooling have a direct effect on the students' mental well-being. The stigma about mental health causes Filipinos experiencing any sort of mental disorder to struggle discussing their condition. The formulated research questions tackle the phenomenon. The following research questions guide this study:

- RQ1: What are the experiences of nursing students that impact their mental health when studying nursing?
- RQ2: What are the themes that surfaced from the experiences of nursing students?
- RQ3: What tool can be developed based on the experiences described by the nursing students?

Methodology

This study used a sequential exploratory design. The researchers utilized this as the overall research design by the proponents as to fulfill the objective to determine the factors or difficulties related of mental health preparedness among BSN students with Related Learning Experience (RLE) and develop a mental health preparedness tool for incoming nursing students at St. Dominic College of Asia.

Twenty-one (21) nursing students who were officially enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Nursing Program at SDCA during the AY 2020-2021 took part in the study. The inclusion criteria were only covered by nursing students with RLE for they are more exposed to stressors, while the exclusion criteria did not cover nursing students with no with RLE. The researchers looked for respondents, who have RLE to gather the necessary data.

The researchers provided the participants a letter of consent and information about the study. The chosen participants were helpful, and the tool would prove beneficial to the nursing students and the institution. This study would also be helpful to families and friends of the client by recognizing mental health problems that necessitates ample social support. In addition, schools and communities would be capable of enhancing their programs towards mental health management to prove advantageous in removing the stigma surrounding mental health.

The sampling technique used is the purposive sampling technique, which is a sampling method where the researchers used a criterion. After the participants have been identified, there was an agreement between the researchers and participants on their participation in the Google survey form. Upon initial interaction, informed consent was given to inform them of their purposes and their rights to confidentiality in this research study.

After the participants have approved, intuition and data collection carried out through a semi-structured type of questions allowing researchers to remain open to meaning as they dig deeper into the phenomenon. The researchers utilized two instruments in this study. In Phase one, the qualitative method was employed through a modified survey created in Google Forms due to restrictions. Even though the instrument was shifted to Google Forms, the researchers assured that this is a comparable method to evoke the experiences of participants so that they will provide the necessary information.

With the aim of having fruitful feedback, the researchers formulated 13 appropriate yet thought-provoking questions to ensure that all topics be tackled and responded to. The questions were validated by their research coordinator and were able to retrieve only 21 nursing students from SDCA.

Problems arose after the data collection was finished. The answers of the participants showed that they were not able to fully express themselves, which made it difficult for the researchers to analyze the data into themes, because the population is not enough to present the whole nursing program of the institution.

After gathering the necessary data, the researchers proceeded to Phase two, which is the quantitative method. They developed a second instrument which is the mental health preparedness tool for nursing students.

The preparedness tool utilized a Likert scale. The test consists of 20 items, where the respondents were requested to answer based on their degree of approval. It offers a private, self-directed survey that may essentially cut the possibility of giving a preconceived notion due to group or public interest.

Scores were tallied and accorded to their respective category to describe the respondent's mental health preparedness. After developing the tool, it was validated by the following experts, a subject matter expert, a psychometrician, and a grammarian.

The established mental health preparedness tool functions as an evaluation and reference point. The test cannot function as a medical diagnosis tool or give any therapeutic claims. Once the test is developed, it will undergo a validity process. The instrument tool should have undergone pilot-testing for its reliability and validity. However, due to difficulties presented during the pandemic, the researchers adjusted to the situation.

The researchers utilized Cronbach's alpha, which they believed that such measure is fit for the mental preparedness tool since it is widely used with the Likert scale to deem if its design and scoring are accurate or not. After data collection is completed, data analysis occurred, wherein the researchers extracted similar concepts translated into specific themes through inductive reasoning.

Results

The Themes that Surfaced from the Experiences of Nursing Students

Figure 1. Themes and subthemes formulated based on the data from qualitative phase

Theme 1: The impact of the course-related experiences on the mental health of Nursing students.

Sub-Theme 1: Choosing nursing as the course in college

Figure 2 shows that 39% of the participants say they are influenced by family members when deciding to pursue a nursing degree. Some participants want to fulfill their parents' or relatives' dream on having a reliable nurse in the family. These responses have shown that members of the family were found to have a significant role that influences the career choice of participants. 18% of the participants planned their course because of personal reasons such as passion, childhood dream, and their desire to help others.

Sub-Theme 2: The experiences in choosing a course in college

Figure 3. The experiences in choosing a course in college

Figure 3 shows that 16% of the participants experienced a dilemma in choosing their college program due to variety of factors that needed to be considered while selecting their career path. 8% of the participants further explained that these factors include their financial difficulties. Another 8% answered academic challenges, 8% expressed their uncertainty, and 12% of the other participants said that they experienced no difficulties while choosing their course.

Sub-Theme 3: Difficulties in choosing the course prior to college admissions

Figure 4. Difficulties in choosing the course prior to college admissions

Figure 4 shows that 16% of the participants experienced a dilemma in choosing their college program due to variety of factors that needed to be considered while selecting their career path. 8% of the participants further explained that these factors include their financial difficulties. Another 8% answered academic challenges, 8% expressed their uncertainty, and 12% of the other participants said that they experienced no difficulties while choosing their course.

Sub-Theme 4: The factors that affected the selection of the course

Majority of the participants decided to take up a Nursing course for themselves, making it the major factor in the respondents' decision of taking Nursing as their course in college with a percentage of 25%. 10% of the participants expressed their passion of providing care, although 15% of the participants expressed their worries about the financial difficulty that they may encounter throughout their journey.

Figure 5. The factors that affected the selection of the course

Sub-Theme 5: The preparation in choosing a course

Figure 6. The preparation in choosing a course

As the researchers culminate the participants' data, it was found out that 23% of the participants said that they did some research about Nursing as part of their preparation in college, thus, putting them in the code of mental preparedness. 12% of the participants also explained that they did not prepare and were carefree.

Sub-Theme 6: The expectations towards nursing before enrollment

Figure 7. The expectations towards nursing before enrollment

When participants were asked about their expectations towards the program, 29% expressed their desire to learn. However, 25% of these participants were concerned of the possible difficulties within the program. Because of this, 9% of them believe that they will suffer fatigue.

Theme 2: Journey as a Nursing student

Sub-Theme 7: The difficulties encountered both in academic and clinical learning experiences

Figure 8. The difficulties encountered both in academic and clinical learning experiences

Majority of the participants expressed their difficulties in both academic and clinical learning experiences. 26% of the participants said that academic challenges were present, and another 26% also expressed that these difficulties make them feel pressured. They also specified these challenges including projects with a tight deadline, cultural differences, lack of time management and many terminologies to memorize.

Sub-Theme 8: The effects of positive and negative opinions towards nursing as a profession, practice, and discipline on the students' course choice

Figure 9. The effects of positive and negative opinions towards nursing as a profession, practice, and discipline on the students' course choice

Overall, the participants shared both positive and negative opinions towards the nursing program. Some of the participants expressed their experiences such as having academic challenges and professional difficulties. When asked how the participants' perception affects their career choice, 14% of the participants expressed their desire to help others, and 11% took these challenges as an opportunity, and encouragement to pursue their determination to care for others.

Sub-Theme 9: The qualities of students that are fitting for nursing as a course

Figure 10. The qualities of students that are fitting for nursing as a course

Researchers asked participants what qualities they have which they think is fit for nursing. 9% of the participants said that knowledge is key to help the sick. 10% of the participants expressed their desire to help others, and 14% are driven by their passion to contribute to the society. 19% also mentioned that a good communication is also important to provide care. Participants also expressed that they like interacting with patience and giving them a better quality of life. Majority of the participants answered caring as the main quality fitting for nursing students with a percentage of 33%.

Sub-Theme 10: The consideration for a change in career/profession

Figure 11. The consideration for a change in career/profession

Participants were asked if they consider changing their career-path. Around 35% of the participants expressed their contentedness in the nursing program. Some participants further explained that they have the passion and enjoyment to continue nursing. Others also expressed their difficulties, but they chose to remain.

Sub-Theme 11: Experiences as a nursing student that affected the mental health

Figure 12. Experiences as a nursing student that affected the mental health

When participants were asked about their experiences as nursing students that affected their mental health, almost half of the answers suggested that academic pressure is a factor with 42%. Several factors were also elaborated, this includes: 17% clinical challenges, 8% academic shock, and 8% knowledge overload. Some participants also expressed their fear of failure when expectations are not met.

Sub-Theme 12: Dealing with the challenges faced by a nursing student

Figure 13. Dealing with the challenges faced by a nursing student

Researchers asked the participants how they handle the challenges they encountered as a nursing student. 37% responded that having a support system helped the respondents in dealing with the challenges they are facing. 18% of the participants explained that by focusing on their academics, they were able to handle their difficulties. Another 18% believe that rewarding oneself, and doing leisure activities help them avoid academic pressures.

Sub-Theme 13: Factors that influenced participants to transfer to St. Dominic College of Asia

Participants who transferred institutions were asked 'What made you change your mind to transfer to St. Dominic College of Asia?' 40% of the participants expressed their admiration for the quality of education in the institution, while 60% of the participants said that the school offers an affordable tuition fee.

However, none of the participants mentioned any experiences that contribute to their mental health. Further questions are needed.

Figure 14. Factors that influenced participants to transfer to St. Dominic College of Asia

Tool that Developed Based on the Experiences Described by the Nursing Students

The instrumental tool is developed using a Likert scale. The items were based on the experiences that were described by the nursing students at SDCA. The researchers tallied the answers based on the themes, and sub-themes.

Table 1. Mental Health Preparedness Tool

No.	Statement	Always (4)	Often (3)	Sometimes (2)	Never (1)
1	My family greatly influences my decisions.				
2	It is difficult for me to decide by myself. I need to ask for opinions from others.				
3	During my college applications, I found it hard to choose a course.				
4	I am confident in taking Nursing as my course.				
5	I am hesitant in taking up Nursing as it requires so much money.				
6	I am mentally prepared because I have done extensive preparation such as researching before entering the Nursing program.				
7	I am mindful that I need to exert extra effort in studying Nursing.				
8	I have encountered difficulties such as stress and pressure lately.				
9	I have trouble managing my time.				
10	I am eager to become a Registered Nurse someday.				
11	I am aware that the Nursing profession is not easy.				
12	I had doubts when I chose Nursing as my major.				
13	I can handle challenges well by looking at them optimistically.				
14	My parents support me in taking up Nursing.				
15	I have the passion for taking care of others.				
16	I am certain that I will enjoy Nursing as my course.				
17	I do not mind working late nights to accomplish schoolwork.				
18	I talk to my peers and friends regarding my feelings/thoughts about Nursing.				
19	I am satisfied with the school that I chose.				
20	I believe I will develop the skills needed to be in the Nursing profession.				

The data collected as well as the themes and codes extracted from the thematic analysis have been considered to formulate the questions. Scores will then be tallied and accorded to their respective category to describe the respondent's mental health preparedness. For proper interpretation, negatively phrased questions, specifically questions number 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 9, and 12 will be scored oppositely; with always = 1, often = 2, sometimes = 3, and never = 4.

Table 2. Categories for evaluating the mental health preparedness of incoming nursing students

Group	Total Score	Impression
Highly adaptive	65-80	Indicates excellent functioning; has little to no risk for mental health problems
Moderately adaptive	50-64	Indicates neutral adaptation; low risk for mental health problems
Partially adaptive	35-49	Indicates some ineffective coping; medium risk for mental health problems
Poorly adaptive	20-34	Indicates maladaptive behavior; highly prone to mental health problems; may need guidance

Discussion

The Experiences of Nursing Students That Impact Their Mental Health When Studying Nursing

The proponents categorized the experiences of the participants into positive and negative experiences to further explore their effects on the participants' mental health.

Negative Experiences. The clinical environment is inherent in training nursing students into professionals. However, in this transition, there are factors that subject nursing students to physical and psychological fatigue (Kalyani et al., 2019). The participants of this study stated their negative experiences from academic and clinical challenges to the uncertainties towards the course and profession. Participants shared their struggle within the clinical environment. Furthermore, the hectic schedules accompanied by difficult and spontaneous tasks added to the emotional distress they had experienced. As a result, some participants expressed their uncertainty in continuing the course or profession.

Shaban et al. (2012) has stated that factors such as heavy workload, a stressful clinical environment, and problems with the nursing staff and instructors have made nursing students dissatisfied with the clinical components provided by an institution. Finally, some participants feel uncertain about choosing nursing as a profession. In the study of Kalyani et al. (2019), the inadequacy of the educational environment had subjected students to question their identity. Furthermore, the lack of management, constructive strategies, and positive influences, made it difficult for nursing students to accept their roles which ultimately impede their development.

Positive Experiences. Amidst the heavy academic workload and strenuous clinical activities, there are still instances wherein the participants of the study came across positive experiences. These moments were present in the participants' relationships, clinical encounters, and their perception towards nursing. Dube and Mlotshwa (2018) further concludes that familial and lecturer-student relationships are factors that influence the academic performances and experiences of students.

Some participants had an enjoyable time while in clinical trials. Ekstedt et al. (2019) stated that nursing students achieve positive experiences within a clinical environment wherein staff and students can engage and collaborate cordially. In a study conducted by Woo and Li (2020), nursing students have positive experiences with a clinical environment that emphasizes clear and organized distribution of tasks among the students and the opportunities for interactions between the students and the instructors.

Despite experiencing heavy academic and work-related stress, nursing students still have a positive perception of the nursing profession. However, instructors and nursing staff must be sensitive about the possible stressors and apply coping strategies that may eliminate the difficulties faced by nursing students (Tseng et al., 2013).

Themes that Surfaced from the Experiences of Nursing Students

Theme 1: The Experiences of Nursing Students that Impact their Mental Health When Studying Nursing

Nursing is generally recognized as a prestigious career in society due to the core principle it promotes in its practice, which is life care. It is important to ascertain how students perceive nursing, and why they decided on nursing as a career. The personal experiences or observations of participants in nurses at work nurture their views on nursing profession.

However, Nursing is undeniably one of the most high-pressured courses to deal as the students are exposed to different levels of stress and pushed beyond their limits as part of their training to become excellent nurses in the field. In previous studies conducted in United States, Iran, Singapore, India, and Malaysia shows that mental health issue is a growing concern among college student (Kamimura et al., 2018) and depression, alcohol use, stress, low sleep quality, excessive daytime sleepiness, and anxiety are major mental health problems among nursing students (Pacheco et al., 2017). "My experiences as a nursing student triggers my mental health in which is, it increases my stress and also my depression from all the pressure from academic and even from the family expectations, which makes my mental health worst" is a response from one of the participants in the study after being asked about their experiences that affects their mental health which is evidently challenging the mental health capacity of nursing students as they thrive to finish the course.

Subtheme 1: Choosing nursing as the course in college. Practical considerations, such as career opportunities, play a large role in deciding whether to pursue nursing (Marcinowicz et al., 2016). These personal reasons may vary to the experiences of the participants. To narrow down the idea, it is important for the researchers to recognize these considerations that influence the respondents' decision in pursuing nursing as their career course.

Subtheme 2: The experiences in choosing a course in college. Experience is one of the factors and has a great impact in decision making. The personal experiences or observations of participants in nurses at work nurture their views on nursing profession. Often these observations were superficial, concerning only selected fragments of nursing work (Marcinowicz et al., 2016). With this, the researchers should acknowledge experiences that a student had before deciding to choose nursing.

Subtheme 3: Difficulties in choosing the course prior to college admissions.

The major you decide on is a decision that could potentially affect you for the rest of your life, or at least for the rest of your college career (Kuehnle, 2017), and it may be linked to the field and profession you will have soon. But there are challenges and problems that can confuse our minds, it may interfere our decision making and when a student is perplexed, there is a possibility that they would struggle facing unexpected challenges because this confusion may arise unpreparedness towards the future or at least the course that they take. The researchers need to know such difficulties that the respondents experienced to further understand, relate, and analyze the factors and participants' data.

Subtheme 4: The factors that affected the selection of the course. The choice of career is a delicate issue for students, which requires caution and serious considerations affecting their choices. It becomes one of the most difficult and challenging in a student's life because it entails the interaction of numerous factors that are primarily associated (Ouano et al., 2019). In connection with the study, Subtheme four correspond to the factors that participants have identified which affect their selection when they chose their nursing college course. The factors that have been gathered will help the researchers to determine if the student was under pressure or dilemma by these identified factors in the time of their decision making.

Subtheme 5: The preparation in choosing a course. Knowing that a Nursing course can cause conflict with schedules, tricky exams, and workloads are piling up constantly, and tons of medical terminologies needed to be put in mind. According to Smith et al. (2019), people who are emotionally and mentally resilient have the tools for coping with difficult situations and maintaining a positive outlook. They remain focused, flexible, and productive, in bad times as well as good. In line with this, the researchers would like to assess if the students were able to prepare for these difficulties that they might experience throughout their journey, starting to their admission to the nursing program to attainment of their degree and job.

Subtheme 6: The expectations towards nursing before enrollment. It has become expedient to identify the perceptions of prospective students about nursing and the reasons for choosing nursing as a career (Ouano et al., 2019). Transition from senior high school to college can be challenging for students as they enter to a new and unfamiliar environment of another level of education. Most of the students who are planning to enter a program in college have their own perception towards the course that they are going to take. Research shows that the positive effects of expectations are most strongly felt at the start of the school year or at the beginning of a new project. This is likely because we tend to start things with a more open mind, and are more open to new possibilities (Stenger, 2019). In relation to the study, expectations of the respondents help them set their mind to things that are possible for them to face in their journey. This serves as another basis for the researchers that the respondents are aware in the outcomes of their decision in choosing nursing.

Theme 2: Journey as a nursing student that impact their mental health when studying nursing.

Nursing school is tough, students are expected to learn a large amount of information and new skills quickly. However, being successful in nursing school requires much more than doing well on homework assignments and thus to meet these requirements. Students are expected to employ these techniques during their course of study (ECPI University, n.d.). Student nurses tends to feel overwhelmed due to heavy workloads and having to balance coursework, exams, skills labs, and clinical rotations simultaneously with personal and family obligations can intensify these feelings, creating a fear of failure. In the participant's point of view, "A nursing student may experience a lot of hard works to become successful. There are sleepless nights and emotional breakdown." With this being expected, it is not enough that students are aware with these kinds of challenges, but it is desirable that they are prepared with it. With this, the researchers want to explore the experiences of student nurses to determine their coping strategies towards these events.

Subtheme 7: The difficulties encountered both in academic and clinical learning experiences. Most of the participants expressed their challenges in both academic and clinical educational environment. Students have reported that the lessons can be sometimes difficult to understand which makes them feel pressured. Difficulties are often an unavoidable but important part of the learning process (Lodge et al., 2018). Identifying the difficulties of the student will establish and narrow down which part of the journey were challenging. At this point, the succeeding researchers will have a chance to construct intervention that will assist student's self-regulation into the educational setting (Lodge et al., 2018).

Subtheme 8: The effects of positive and negative opinions towards nursing as a profession, practice, and discipline on the students' course choice. Personal reasons are more dominant than career related. Students said that despite the challenges they encounter in the nursing program, they are still determined to graduate so that they can help others. The researchers believe that these data will show how the students handle their opinions with regards to their profession. Tabassum (2019) believed that listening to people's opinion is commendable but precarious to get influenced by them.

Subtheme 9: The qualities of students that are fitting for nursing as a course. The participants expressed their difficulties; however, they believe that they are compassionate to pursue nursing. They further explained that they like to communicate with their patients and provide quality of care to improve their quality of life. The researchers believe that this is a positive experience for nursing students because it encourages the students to become more determine in their promising careers. This may also improve their academic performances. As stated by Chowdhury (2019) positive psychology has a potential in improving the well-being of a person. Studies have shown that the effect of positive psychology produces more happiness and lessen the risk of having mental health illnesses. According to Cornell and Vaughn (2020), caring is the top quality a student must have because having the ability to make the patient feel cared is a significant indicator of nurse's success. In line with this, the researchers believe that it is crucial to understand the characteristics fit to the said course as it will affect the performance of the student during the clinical duty.

Subtheme 10: The consideration for a change in career/profession. Attending college can be a stressful time for students. An overwhelming environment can be too much for them to handle. According to Pedrelli et al. (2015) many college students experience onset of mental health symptoms. Because of this, students may doubt the chosen major and might consider in changing careers. Fortunately, all the participants expressed their satisfaction of their course. They will continue pursuing their nursing careers.

Subtheme 11: Experiences as a nursing student that affected the mental health. College students face significant challenges to their mental health. According to Timmins et al. (2011), academic and clinical components of the nursing curriculum can be stressful for students. In their study, it is evident that students' stress is related to their nursing program. These include examinations, return demonstrations, and studies in general. The researchers found evident results that the nursing students of SDCA also experienced stressors on their course. Many expressed that they are stressed because of academic pressure, clinical challenges, and knowledge overload. When expectations are not met, they have fears of failure. These factors significantly affect a student's mental health and are at risk of developing mental health illnesses.

Subtheme 12: Dealing with the challenges faced by a nursing student. According to Al-Zayyat and Al-Gamal (2014), it is inevitable for nursing students to receive stress from their course. They further explained that coping mechanisms are important to navigate their life. Nursing students must learn positive coping mechanisms to reduce the risk of mental health illnesses. These coping strategies may help them to provide more care to their patients. Students have reported that having a support system helps them in dealing with the stress from academics, as well as rewarding oneself. It is evident that nursing students of SDCA are aware of their coping mechanisms.

Subtheme 13: Factors that influenced participants to transfer to St. Dominic College of Asia. Transferring institutions from one school to another gives worries to college students. Many students transfer because they are unhappy of their social situation. Students may feel isolated from their institution or simply not the right environment for them. Financial situation can also be a factor. Students may feel the need to transfer colleges because of unforeseen expenses (Gaffney, 2020). Transferred students said that their reason was to find a more affordable tuition fee. They further expressed how SDCA is the right institution to attend to.

Tool That Developed Based on the Experiences Described by the Nursing Students

The Mental Health Preparedness tool is composed of a 20-item questionnaire which is based on the analysis of raw data from the collected responses in the survey composed of 13 questions. It comprises of a 4-point Likert scale calculating with a total score of 80 as the highest and a 20 as the lowest. The evaluation is divided into four categories with the impression of how much adapting or coping skill a respondent has.

Circling back to the Adaptation Model, the categories for evaluating the mental health preparedness of the incoming nursing students measure how much their adaptation level is. They can either be highly, moderately, partially, or poorly adaptive.

The codes and themes developed were essential in the formulation of these categories (Saldaña, 2009). The researchers were able to assign an interpretation to a respondent's score to indicate effective functioning or any maladaptive behavior. Such can be vital in observing adaptation: the success (or failure) of coping, and risk for mental health problems.

Since the theoretical basis of this study is Roy's Adaptation Model, the researchers were mindful of its assumptions, whether it be explicit or implicit, during the thematic analysis. To expound, the Adaptation Model claims that the 'Person' has four modes of adaptation: physiologic needs, self-concept, role function, and interdependence (Dayılar Candan et al., 2022); all of which were reflected in the responses in the survey. Like how interdependence is seen in the participants' decision-making being heavily influenced by family, physiologic needs with the support system, whereas self-concept and role function being inferred in their passion, desire to learn, and other related skills.

Moreover, the researchers were able to process and organize the raw data by coding the participants' responses that aided in formulating the tool questions, because long responses is limited to four precise categories as appropriate in the preparedness tool. Assigning codes to words and phrases in each response helped capture what the response entails which, in turn, leads to better breakdown of the results of the entire survey. The responses of the participants were all coded and then tallied. The leading codes from each question in the survey became the basis of the Mental Health Preparedness tool. The common responses enclosed within the leading codes were rephrased to ensure that all the questions made for MHP tool were entirely based on the results of the researchers' survey and study.

Conclusions

This study aims to create a Mental Health Preparedness tool for students who wish to pursue a nursing degree. Based on the findings, the experiences of nursing students are divided into two categories, positive and negative. The learning academe of nursing has contributed positive feedback from the students. There are many factors that have surfaced but most expressed their desire to help others and passion acts as a driving force for the students to continue pursuing a nursing degree. However, the students expressed difficulties in the program. Anxiety and depression are the most common factors that affect their learning performances. Because of this, they are at risk of developing symptoms of mental health disorders. The researchers determined that academic pressure was the leading difficulty experienced by the participants. The compliance with academic requirements has great effect on the nursing student's mental health (Saloman, 2019). Moreover, another study emphasizes the importance of time management and satisfying well-being in the improvement of learning (Rosvall, 2019). Financial difficulties are part of the factors in their mental health. It pressures the students to attend college as it is value for a successful life. Participants also expressed their laborious amount of workload and are pressured to keep up with the requirements. Assessing the mental preparedness of incoming nursing students is vital to the development or improvement of coping systems and mental health programs. This study shows the environment can affect a student's mental health. In a study conducted by VanderLind (2017), he mentioned that mental illnesses are linked to a decrease in academic performances and degree completion.

Even with numerous hardships, students of SDCA were able to adapt to their environment with their own coping strategies and being optimistic. As expressed by Roy's Adaptive Model, a person should possess adequate adaptive skills, both innate and acquired to cope in an ever-changing world. Nursing, initially being a family-influenced choice of course for most, became a fulfilling endeavor despite clinical and academic hardships. As stated by Puthran et al. (2016), students who know how to fully adapt and armed with effective coping strategies are likely to control academic demands.

Two themes and 13 sub-themes emerged from the answers of the participants. It enables the data to be flexible in interpretation. These findings are crucial to the development of the Mental Health Preparedness Tool. The developed Mental Health Preparedness tool would be an objective guide to assess the students' level of functioning when faced with distress. A student's mental readiness, coupled with skill, a proper support system, and healthy coping patterns is a formula for finding success in the nursing curricula, and eventually, the profession. Researchers retain most of the methods that were not utilized for this study for the future researchers and readers who will be interested in continuing this study. Researchers still believe that these methods are essential in developing, validating, and testing an instrumental tool.

The researchers determined that the mental health preparedness tool cannot be as effective in assessing the incoming nursing student's adaptability to stressors in the course as it did not undergo a pilot-testing. It is assumed then that the tool is not reliable and valid enough for administration. It is far from complete as this study needs further time and development to improve.

Recommendations

This study utilizes Callista Roy's adaptation model to discover insights on the mental health situation of nursing students eventually creating an assessment tool concerning their mental preparedness and adaptability towards the nursing course. Study finds that there is a connection between the psychological adaptation and mental health of nursing students. Students may show evidence of strain and become symptomatic and impaired in their functioning while studying (Notman et al., 1984). Zhou and Lin (2016) further explained that adaptability is a significant aspect in positive psychology. Individuals who have stronger adaptability can easily adjust themselves in the new environment. Adaptability will have more positive impact in life satisfaction when combined with social support. Although there are studies to support these claims, it is recommended to conduct further research on the correlation between two variables. Researchers also suggest looking more applicable theories for this study to further reach unexplored factors that affect mental health.

Aside from producing an assessment tool for entry level nursing students, the developed tool could also act as bridge to alleviate some of the pressures and anxieties experienced by nursing students. Professors or clinical instructors would be informed of the difficulties faced by their students and can adjust according to their level of coping skill. In turn, students who answer the tool may be more prudent before they start their journey in nursing.

The fine line between maladaptive behavior and healthy coping mechanisms should be clearly defined to distinguish if an individual is prone to experience impaired functioning. With ample collaboration among nursing researchers and educators, the establishment of the Mental Health Preparedness tool would become optimal. It can also be tapered to fit other collegiate degrees besides nursing. Further testing or modifications to the tool would be left in the hands of other researchers.

Although this study has answered the research questions, the methods used could have been more effective. With the Covid-19 pandemic, the researchers adapted the new normal data collection through Google survey form. Because of this, the participants were not able to fully express their experiences. Therefore, responses are considered insufficient. It is advised to use newer and more effective method for the data collection process like an online focus group via zoom, and more open-ended question so participants can express more freely and discover new insights that will help the study. It is also advised to gather numerous participants to appropriately present the nursing student as the basis for the instrumental tool. In data analysis, researchers recommend broadening and merge similar sub-themes to fully differentiate themes and sub-themes. It is recommended to strictly follow the thematic analysis guide of Castleberry and Nolen (2018).

For the Mental Health Preparedness Tool, a pilot-test is mandatory to examine its reliability and validity before disseminating to the respondents. It will also assess if the tool is realistic and workable and allows weak test items to be improved to capture the intended concept. Studies show that regardless of demographic and socioeconomic status, everyone can develop symptoms of mental health disorders. For future implications of this study, the researchers then suggest adding demographic and socioeconomic status of nursing students to further improve the tool. Moreover, they recommend studying the correlation of adaptation and mental readiness as well as the effectiveness of the mental health preparedness tool, because this study needs more time and further improvement before it can be properly administered in the institution.

References

- Al-Zayyat, A. S., & Al-Gamal, E. (2014). Perceived stress and coping strategies among Jordanian nursing students during clinical practice in psychiatric/mental health courses. *International Journal of Mental Health Nursing*, 23(4), 326-335. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inm.12054>
- Barrett, P., & Jackson, A. (2013). Swimming without the water: A critical perspective on mental health experience for adult nursing students. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 13(6), 487-491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2013.05.002>
- Barry, S., & Ward, L. (2017). Undergraduate nursing students' understandings of mental health: A review of the literature. *Issues in Mental Health Nursing*, 38(2), 160-175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01612840.2016.1251515>
- Beauvais, A. M. (Ed.). (2018). *Leadership and management competence in nursing practice: Competencies, skills, decision-making*. Springer Publishing Company.

- Castleberry, A., & Nolen, A. (2018). Thematic analysis of qualitative research data: Is it as easy as it sounds? *Currents in Pharmacy Teaching and Learning*, 10(6), 807-815. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cptl.2018.03.019>
- Cheung, T., Wong, S. Y., Wong, K. Y., Law, L. Y., Ng, K., Tong, M. T., Wong, K. Y., Ng, M. Y., & Yip, P. S. (2016). Depression, anxiety and symptoms of stress among baccalaureate nursing students in Hong Kong: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 13(8), 779. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph13080779>
- Chowdhury, M. R. (2019, April 9). *The neuroscience of gratitude and effects on the brain*. Positive Psychology. <https://positivepsychology.com/neuroscience-of-gratitude/>
- Conley, D. T. (2007). *Redefining college readiness*. Educational Policy Improvement Center. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED539251.pdf>
- Cornell, A., & Vaughn, N. (2020, February 25). *13 qualities of a good nurse: Leadership & personality characteristics*. Relias. <https://www.relias.com/blog/13-qualities-and-characteristics-of-a-good-nurse>
- Damiano, P., Momany, E., McNroy, B., Bentler, S., & Heeren, T. (2017). *Experiences of adults and children in the Iowa Medicaid integrated health home program*. University of Iowa Public Policy Center. <https://iro.uiowa.edu/esploro/outputs/report/Experiences-of-Adults-and-Children-in/9983557298802771>
- Dayılar Candan, H., Doğan, S., Güler, C., & Carroll, K. (2022). Roy adaptation model: Theory-based knowledge and nursing care with a person experiencing COVID-19. *Nursing Science Quarterly*, 35(3), 304-310. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08943184221092434>
- DeAngelis, T. (2015, March). *In search of cultural competence*. American Psychological Association. <https://www.apa.org/monitor/2015/03/cultural-competence>
- Dube, M. B., & Mlotshwa, P. R. (2018). Factors influencing enrolled nursing students' academic performance at a selected private nursing education institution in KwaZulu-Natal. *Curationis*, 41(1), a1850. <https://doi.org/10.4102/curationis.v41i1.1850>
- ECPI University. (n.d.). *Expectations for nursing students: What will my degree program require?* <https://www.ecpi.edu/blog/expectations-for-nursing-students-what-will-my-degree-program-expect>
- Ekstedt, M., Lindblad, M., & Löfmark, A. (2019). Nursing students' perception of the clinical learning environment and supervision in relation to two different supervision models—a comparative cross-sectional study. *BMC Nursing*, 18, 49. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-019-0375-6>
- Gaffney, J. L. (2020). *Your story is your strength: Developing an ethic of care through transformative learning* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Wisconsin – Stevens Point). <https://minds.wisconsin.edu/bitstream/handle/1793/80262/C1%20Gaffney%20final.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Kalyani, M. N., Jamshidi, N., Molazem, Z., Torabizadeh, C., & Sharif, F. (2019). How do nursing students experience the clinical learning environment and respond to their experiences? A qualitative study. *BMJ Open*, 9(7), e028052. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-028052>
- Kamimura, A., Trinh, H. N., Johansen, M., Hurley, J., Pye, M., Sin, K., & Nguyen, H. (2018). Perceptions of mental health and mental health services among college students in Vietnam and the United States. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 37, 15-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2018.07.012>
- Kessler, R. C., Amminger, G. P., Aguilar-Gaxiola, S., Alonso, J., Lee, S., & Üstün, T. B. (2007). Age of onset of mental disorders: A review of recent literature. *Current Opinion in Psychiatry*, 20(4), 359-364. <https://doi.org/10.1097/YCO.0b013e32816ebc8c>
- Kuehnle, A. (2017, September 26). *The difficulties of choosing a college major*. Odyssey. <https://www.theodysseyonline.com/difficulties-choosing-college-major>
- Lally, J., Samaniego, R. M., & Tully, J. (2019). Mental health legislation in the Philippines: Philippine Mental Health Act. *BJPsych International*, 16(3). <https://doi.org/10.1192/bji.2018.33>
- Lodge, J. M., Kennedy, G., Lockyer, L., Arguel, A., & Pachman, M. (2018). Understanding difficulties and resulting confusion in learning: An integrative review. *Frontiers in Education*, 3, 49. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2018.00049>
- Marcinowicz, L., Owlasz, A., Slusarska, B., Zarzycka, D., & Pawlikowska, T. (2016). Choice and perception of the nursing profession from the perspective of Polish nursing students: A focus group study. *BMC Medical Education*, 16, 243. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-016-0765-3>
- Notman, M. T., Salt, P., & Nadelson, C. C. (1984). Stress and adaptation in medical students: Who is most vulnerable? *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 25(3), 355-366. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-440X\(84\)90068-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-440X(84)90068-3)
- Ouano, J. J. G., Torre, J. F. D. L., Japitan, W. I., & Moneva, J. C. (2019). Factors influencing on grade 12 students' chosen courses in Jagobiao National High School—senior high school department. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 9(1), 421-431. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.9.01.2019.p8555>
- Pacheco, J. P., Giacomini, H. T., Tam, W. W., Ribeiro, T. B., Arab, C., Bezerra, I. M., & Pinasco, G. C. (2017). Mental health problems among medical students in Brazil: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Brazilian Journal of Psychiatry*, 39(4), 369-378. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1516-4446-2017-2223>
- Pedrelli, P., Nyer, M., Yeung, A., Zulauf, C., & Wilens, T. (2015). College students: mental health problems and treatment considerations. *Academic Psychiatry*, 39, 503-511. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40596-014-0205-9>
- Puthran, R., Zhang, M. W. B., Tam, W. W., & Ho, R. C. (2016). Prevalence of depression amongst medical students: A meta-analysis. *Medical Education*, 50(4), 456-468. <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.12962>
- Reality Changers. (2017, April 27). *College readiness: The importance of preparing for college while in high school*. <https://realitychangers.org/college-readiness-importance-preparing-college-high-school/>
- Rezayat, F., & Nayeri, N. D. (2014). The level of depression and assertiveness among nursing students. *International Journal of Community Based Nursing and Midwifery*, 2(3), 177-184. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4201197/pdf/ijcbbnm-2-177.pdf>

- Rosvall, P. Å. (2020). Perspectives of students with mental health problems on improving the school environment and practice. *Education Inquiry*, 11(3), 159-174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20004508.2019.1687394>
- Saldaña, J. (2009). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*. Sage Publications Ltd.
- Saloman, L. (2019, April 29). *Depression and anxiety in college students: A true epidemic?* Psycom. <https://www.psycom.net/depression-anxiety-college-students>
- Shaban, I. A., Khater, W. A., & Akhu-Zaheya, L. M. (2012). Undergraduate nursing students' stress sources and coping behaviours during their initial period of clinical training: A Jordanian perspective. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 12(4), 204-209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2012.01.005>
- Shamsuddin, K., Fadzil, F., Ismail, W. S. W., Shah, S. A., Omar, K., Muhammad, N. A., Jaffar, A., Ismail, A., & Mahadevan, R. (2013). Correlates of depression, anxiety and stress among Malaysian university students. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 6(4), 318-323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2013.01.014>
- Smith, M., Segal, R., Robinson, L., & Segal, J. (2019). *Building better mental health*. Help Guide. <https://www.helpguide.org/articles/mental-health/building-better-mental-health.htm>
- Stenger, M. (2019, February 19). *How expectations influence performance*. InformED. <https://www.opencolleges.edu.au/informed/features/expectations-influence-performance/>
- Tabassum. (2019, April 17). *Are your opinions influenced?* Voices of Youth. <https://www.voicesofyouth.org/blog/are-our-opinions-influenced>
- Timmins, F., Corroon, A. M., Byrne, G., & Mooney, B. (2011). The challenge of contemporary nurse education programmes. Perceived stressors of nursing students: Mental health and related lifestyle issues. *Journal of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing*, 18(9), 758-766. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2850.2011.01780.x>
- Tseng, H. C., Wang, H. H., & Weng, W. C. (2013). Nursing students' perceptions toward the nursing profession from clinical practicum in a baccalaureate nursing program—A qualitative study. *The Kaohsiung Journal of Medical Sciences*, 29(3), 161-168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kjms.2012.08.027>
- VanderLind, R. (2017). Effects of mental health on student learning. *The Learning Assistance Review*, 22(2), 39-58. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1154566>
- Woo, M. W. J., & Li, W. (2020). Nursing students' views and satisfaction of their clinical learning environment in Singapore. *Nursing Open*, 7(6), 1909-1919. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nop2.581>
- Wynaden, D. (2010). There is no health without mental health: Are we educating Australian nurses to care for the health consumer of the 21st century? *International Journal of Mental Health Nursing*, 19(3), 203-209. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1447-0349.2010.00671>
- Zhou, M., & Lin, W. (2016). Adaptability and life satisfaction: The moderating role of social support. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 1134. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01134>